

CONSIDERATION OF THE INFLUENCING VARIABLES OF PEEL PLY ON THE REACTION PROCESS OF CFRP SAMPLES UNDER LIQUID OXYGEN ENVIRONMENT AT IMPACT LOAD

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Keywords: Composite Material, Cryogenic Fuel Tanks, Liquid Oxygen, Impact, Influencing Variables,

ABSTRACT

Various characterization and certification processes are required for the use of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) in the aerospace industry. This applies in particular if the material is in contact with reactive liquids. However, this poses a number of challenges, as the liquid oxygen used as an oxidizer, for example, can undergo a thermal reaction with the organic substances in the CFRP [1]. This highly exothermic reaction leads to a catastrophic failure of the entire launch vehicle. For this reason, it is essential to determine the compatibility of the tank materials used for the storage of liquid oxygen [2]. Several compatibility tests carried out at *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* have shown that the results obtained are sometimes subject to extreme fluctuations, which can lead to inconsistent statements about material compatibility. The influencing variables that affect the reaction process are partly unknown and are not taken into account in the standard. Based on the known problem, a newly developed test rig was set up at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich*. The influence of the use of peel ply on the compatibility results was explicitly investigated. As a result of the stripping process, rough ridges and irregularities remain on the surface. The roughness of the component surface, caused by cavities, indentations, and surface irregularities, along with local dry spots, leads to increased reactivity of the sample in a liquid oxygen environment. As part of a series of tests to determine the influencing variables on the reaction process of carbon fibre-reinforced plastics in liquid oxygen, it was demonstrated on the test bench at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* that the chemical reactivity of the samples increases when using peel ply.

1 INTRODUCTION

The majority of reusable launch vehicles currently in use and those planned for the future are designed for operation with liquid propellants, using liquid oxygen (LOX) as the oxidizing agent. The state of the art to date comprises metallic tank structures that are used in current generations of launch vehicles. These structures account for over 60 % of the dry mass of a launch vehicle [3]. To increase the payload capacity, it is essential to reduce the dry mass. By using carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), weight savings of up to 40 % could be achieved [3].

However, the compatibility of CFRP materials with the LOX oxidizing agent used is a critical factor. A material is considered compatible if it does not react with LOX or potential ignition sources under the expected pressure and temperature conditions [4]. The avoidance of ignition events is therefore essential for the selection of suitable materials for LOX contact applications. Ignition can occur if a sufficiently high amount of energy is applied locally to the surface exposed to the LOX like shown in Figure 1 for a CFRP test Sample.

Figure 1 Exemplary reaction of a CFRP sample in liquid oxygen, in which an impact pulse of 98 J is transmitted into the sample via a Striker Pin and recorded at 240 FPS using a slow-motion camera

The compatibility of a material for use under cryogenic LOX conditions is assessed using standardized test methods. The relevant test standards include ASTM G86-17 [5], ASTM D2512-95 [6] and ISO 21010 [7]. Common to all methods is the transfer of kinetic energy into the material sample, which leads to an exothermic reaction with LOX in the event of incompatibility. According to ASTM G86, a material is considered compatible if no reaction occurs after 20 tests or at most one reaction after 60 tests.

A comparison of the test results according to different standards shows some considerable deviations in the assessment of LOX compatibility. The reasons for this have not yet been conclusively clarified. Although the oxidation and ignition mechanism itself is well described [4], there is a lack of reliable explanations for the random nature of the reactions and the deviations between the standards. A deeper understanding of these mechanisms is required to ensure reproducible and reliable test results for future material certifications.

The need for research therefore lies in the investigation of the reaction mechanisms of CFRP materials in contact with LOX and the identification of relevant influencing variables - particularly with regard to test stand design, sample preparation and surface properties. Experimental investigations were carried out at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* to analyze the influence of the sample surface on the reaction behavior. The surface topography was specifically varied by using different peel ply fabrics during laminate production. The aim is not only to determine the general influence of the surface roughness on the reaction behavior, but also to identify the causes of increased reactions.

2 STATE OF THE ART

Liquid-propellant rocket engines are widely used in modern spaceflight. With the emergence of the “New Space” movement and the development of new European launch vehicles (e.g., *Ariane 6*, *HyImpulse*, *Rocketfactory Augsburg*, *Isar Aerospace*), the demand for improved cryogenic tank systems has significantly increased. To reduce structural weight and maximize payload capacity, advanced lightweight composite materials are being integrated into launch vehicle architectures—both for primary and secondary propellant tanks. These tank structures can account for up to 60% of a launch vehicle’s dry mass [3].

Future launch systems require a high propellant mass fraction to ensure performance and cost-efficiency. Due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs) are well-suited for achieving these objectives. Liquid oxygen (LOX), serving as the oxidizer in most modern vehicles such as *Ariane 6* and *Falcon 9*, is a key driver in material selection for cryogenic tanks. While CFRP-based LOX tanks offer considerable weight savings, their use introduces challenges due to potential chemical reactivity with LOX. For a material to be considered LOX-compatible, it must withstand all forms of combustible or hazardous reactions under operating conditions [10].

Material compatibility is typically assessed through a set of standardized test methods, including:

- ASTM D2512: Standard Test Method for Compatibility of Materials with Liquid Oxygen [6]
- ASTM G86-17: Determination of Mechanical Impact Sensitivity in LOX and Pressurized Oxygen Environments [5]
- ISO 21010: Compatibility of Gases and Materials in Cryogenic Containers [7]
- NASA-STD-6001: Material Flammability, Offgassing, Odor, and Compatibility Requirements [8]

At the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich*, investigations focused specifically on the influence of surface topography on reaction behavior. Prior research by *Gerzeski* [4] demonstrated that mechanical impact alone is not the sole ignition driver; surface-induced friction plays a significant role. *Gerzeski* proposed a probabilistic model combining Hertzian fracture theory and kinetic friction mechanisms to describe the transition from mechanical failure to heat generation. His findings suggest that surface irregularities, such as those introduced by peel ply usage, can result in local frictional heating, increasing the likelihood of ignition. This mechanism aligns with the so-called “hot spot” theory, widely cited in the literature as the primary cause of polymer reactivity in LOX environments. *Hongyu et al.* [9] reported that localized energy input from friction or impact can decompose polymer chains, releasing reactive hydrogen and hydroxide ions that violently react with LOX, leading to ignition or explosion. Similarly, *Li et al.* [3] describe thermal decomposition of the epoxy matrix as the key trigger for LOX reactivity, again emphasizing the role of temperature-induced hot spots.

Currie et al. [11], the addition of silicon carbide was shown to significantly increase reaction sensitivity in impact LOX tests. Its abrasive nature promotes local heating at the material surface, intensifying both reaction frequency and severity.

Similar investigations were conducted by *Duo et al.* [12], who provided a detailed analysis of the energy transfer process between the striker pin and the specimen surface. Their findings indicate that a significant portion of the mechanical impact energy is converted into heat, with localized temperature increases of several hundred degrees Celsius observed. The quality of the contact interface between the striker and the specimen, as well as the precise impact location, were identified as key factors influencing the test outcomes. According to *Duo et al.* [12], approximately 25% of the kinetic energy is dissipated through friction, while the remainder is transformed into internal energy. This frictional heating can raise local temperatures beyond the decomposition threshold of the epoxy matrix. As a result, highly reactive hydroxyl radicals are generated, which subsequently react with the surrounding liquid oxygen, potentially triggering an exothermic event.

The current study aims to investigate the formation of surface hot spots on CFRP specimens, focusing on resin-rich microstructures caused by different peel ply treatments during laminate fabrication.

3 STANDARDIZED TESTING METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

As part of the conducted experimental series to determine the influencing factors of auxiliary materials on the reaction behavior of CFRP specimens in liquid oxygen under impact loading, tests were carried out according to ASTM G86-17. The standardized procedure involves dropping a defined mass from a specified height onto a striker pin positioned directly on the specimen. The goal is to apply an impact energy of 98 J to the sample, derived from a 9.1 kg drop mass released from a height of 1.1 m. During the test, the specimen is placed in a test cup filled with liquid oxygen. Material incompatibility with LOX is identified based on the following observable criteria [5]:

1. Audible explosion
2. Flash (visually or electronically detected)
3. Signs of combustion, such as visible charring
4. Significant discoloration due to ignition
5. Measurable increases in temperature or pressure during testing

According to ASTM G86, a material is considered compatible if none of these reactions occur in 20 tests or if no more than one reaction is observed in 60 tests. The test specimens used are circular CFRP flat samples with a diameter of 17.5 mm and a thickness of approximately 2 mm. The ASTM G86 [5]

standard also requires the test setup to be kept as clean and contaminant-free as possible. Accordingly, the testing at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* is performed, exceeding standard requirements, in a cleanroom environment. The test cup, striker pin, and CFRP samples are thoroughly cleaned prior to each run. During testing, the fall time is measured to verify compliance with the expected energy input. The measured fall time must not deviate by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the calculated target.

In the context of this scientific investigation, the focus was not on a standard qualification test of the material but rather on identifying the influence of the peel ply treatment on the reaction behavior. For this reason, deviations from the standard procedure, specifically in terms of impact energy and number of trials, were intentionally introduced. These modifications are explained in greater detail in **Chapter 4**.

The LOX impact test facility developed at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 2 Test facility at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* for determining the LOX compatibility of CFRP specimens. a) External view of the test setup inside the cleanroom. b) Close-up of the test device where the drop weight impacts the striker. c) Technical illustration of the individual components of the test rig, consisting of the drop weight and the test chamber containing the specimen immersed in liquid oxygen

To ensure cleanliness during testing and minimize external influences on the experimental procedure, the test bench is located in a cleanroom certified according to ISO 14644 providing an air quality rating of ISO 8. The test facility at the *University of the Bundeswehr Munich* features a modular design that enables LOX compatibility testing across various energy levels. Both the drop height and the drop mass can be flexibly adjusted. Advanced sensor technology allows not only visual and acoustic monitoring of the test but also extended analytical evaluation of the reaction behavior. A fully automated pneumatic adjustment unit enables single-operator testing. Key parameters such as drop mass, fall time, and rebound height are displayed and logged via the integrated HMI system.

The test bench is enclosed in a completely darkened housing, which allows detection of even the smallest reaction events on the specimen. In addition, protective side panels shield the operator from any fragments ejected during specimen failure. To enhance safety and maintain cleanliness within the test chamber, a specialized CFPR vacuum extraction system is employed. This unit removes combustion gases and airborne debris, thereby minimizing contamination and maintaining optimal testing conditions.

4 PREPARATION OF TEST SPECIMENS AND SETUP OF LOX IMPACT TESTING

As part of the experimental campaign to investigate influencing factors on the reaction behavior of CFRP specimens under impact loading in liquid oxygen, a total of five laminate panels were manufactured. Each panel yielded 80 circular test specimens. The only variable among the panels was the type of auxiliary material (peel ply) used during fabrication. All specimens were cured

simultaneously in the same autoclave cycle.

It is well documented in the literature that surface condition can significantly influence test outcomes, as it affects frictional behavior during mechanical loading. Increased friction leads to localized temperature rises, resulting in so-called “hot spots” that promote the thermal decomposition of the epoxy matrix and may trigger a chain reaction with liquid oxygen. However, it remains unclear whether a generally rough surface is sufficient to increase reactivity, or whether the degree of surface roughness also plays a measurable role. A further question is whether surface features introduced by peel ply treatments alter the contact area between the striker and the specimen, thereby affecting the energy transmitted per unit area.

4.1 Fabrication of CFRP Test Samples

To investigate this, specimens with different frictional characteristics were prepared while all other material and process variables remained constant. The aim of the study is to evaluate the influence of surface roughness generated by different peel ply materials on the reactivity of CFRP samples. The results are compared to a reference specimen, referred to as the base plate (GP), produced without peel ply and featuring a smooth surface. **Table 1** lists the fabricated plates together with their designations, the achieved surface-roughness values, and the measured fiber volume content (FVC).

Specimen ID	Peel-Plie	FVC [%]	Ra [μm]	Rz [μm]
GP	none	66,69	0,28	1,95
AB68L-1	Peel ply 68 gsm	65,67	8,91	56,76
AB90L-2	Peel ply 90 gsm	66,97	12,80	78,57
AB100K-4	Peel ply 100 gsm	66,42	9,59	63,9
BLB- 5	Bleeder Lease	68,67	9,0	56,89

Table 1 Overview of the fabricated plates, including their designations, achieved surface roughness values, and measured fiber volume content (FVC).

For this test, all panels were made from Hexply 8552 prepreg with a symmetric 0/90 Orientation. In total 16 Layers were used to obtain a plate thickness of approximately 2 mm. During the laying process, an intermediate vacuum was drawn every 5 layers to achieve the best possible quality. To determine the surface roughness a 3D laser scanning microscope was used. The fiber volume fraction of the CFRP specimens was determined by a loss-on-ignition analysis, in which the polymer matrix was completely removed by pyrolytic burn-off in a muffle furnace.

Figure 3 shows the surface of the fabricated specimens, which differ only in the peel ply used.

Figure 3 comparison of the surface structures of the manufactured test specimens. The texture of the respective peel ply is transferred to the specimen surface upon its removal. The pictures were taken with a digital microscope VH-ZST from Keyence with a dual zoom lens. All images were taken with the ZS 20 lens at a magnification of 100

The analysis of the surface topographies recorded after removal of the peel ply reveals pronounced differences between the specimens. Firstly, peel plies with different weave architectures were used,

resulting in variations in the spacing between warp and weft yarns. Secondly, the number of binding points per unit area differs among the samples. A detailed examination of the surfaces and their correlation with the LOX results is presented in **Chapter 5. Table 2** summarizes the auxiliary materials employed and their relevant properties.

Peel Ply [g/m ²]	Weave pattern	Fineness [dtex]	Material	Properties
Peel-Plie 68 g/qm	plain weave	Warp yarns 44 Weft yarns 78	PA 6.6	Finely textured, rough surface
Peel-Plie 90 g/qm	plain weave	Warp & weft 235	PA 6.6	Finely textured, rough surface
Peel-Plie 100 g/qm	2/2 twill	Warp & weft 235	PA 6.6	Finely textured, rough surface
Bleeder Lease B 62 g/qm	plain weave	-	Nylon	Coated with silicone release,

Table 2 Summary of the release fabrics used for the tests to determine the influencing factors on the reaction process under impact loading in a liquid oxygen environment

4.2 Surface Characterization:

To quantify surface roughness, selected specimens were analyzed using a confocal 3D laser scanning microscope (Keyence VK-X series). These measurements provided both qualitative surface images and quantitative roughness data. An example result is shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 Representation of the analysis of a specimen labeled AB90L-2. Both the raw image of the specimen and the recorded depth profile are shown. The surface roughness was measured along the yellow marking on the specimen. The analysis of the overall profile on the right side of the figure shows the height differences on the surface of the profile.

In addition to roughness values, the contact area between the striker and the specimen must also be assessed to evaluate the relationship between peel ply surface and material reactivity: The results of these investigations are summarized in **Chapter 5**.

In addition to the characterization of surface roughness parameters, further investigations were carried out regarding the peak density (*Spd*), reduced peak height (*Spk*), and peak material volume (*vpm*). An evaluation of these parameters is presented in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5 Analysis of the sample surface with respect to the number of peaks, peak height, and peak material volume. The peaks, consisting of matrix material, are formed by the weave structure of the peel ply and appear on the surface after the removal of the release fabric. This could affect the reactivity of the material regarding the LOX-compatibility

The Spd (peak density) parameter describes the number of surface summits per unit area. A higher Spd value indicates a greater number of potential contact points with interacting surfaces, which can be relevant for tribological performance or adhesion behavior. The Spk (reduced peak height) parameter refers to the average height of the surface peaks above the core material surface and provides information about the prominence of surface asperities. In contrast, the Vpm (peak material volume) parameter quantifies the material volume present at a specified bearing area of p %. Beyond this, Vpm is also used to derive volumetric characteristics of the surface, including the size of the core area, the volume of reduced peaks, and the volume of reduced valleys, thereby contributing to a more detailed assessment of the functional surface profile.

To determine a significant influence between the generated rough surface and the reaction behaviour in liquid oxygen, additional parameters beyond the roughness values must be evaluated. Particular attention must be paid to the area on which the striker rests prior to impact. Reducing this contact area increases the energy input per unit area under otherwise identical conditions. Consequently, more energy is transferred into the specimen as the resin-rich peaks are indented. The causal relationship is discussed in greater detail in Chapter 5.

4.3 Test procedure

After waterjet cutting, the specimens were cleaned with isopropanol and placed in a desiccator for 48 hours. Subsequently, they were conditioned for an additional 72 hours in a controlled climate chamber to eliminate any environmental influences, particularly humidity, that could affect reactivity.

Prior to each test series, the entire test chamber and surrounding area are thoroughly cleaned. Test cups and striker pins are cleaned in an ultrasonic bath after every ten tests. Before reuse, striker pins are also cleaned with isopropanol and degassed in an oven. After cooling, they are ready for operation. To prepare for testing, the striker pins and specimen cups are precooled in a liquid nitrogen bath. The specimens themselves are cooled in liquid oxygen immediately before testing. Once all test components have reached the required temperature, they are placed into the test chamber, which is then filled with liquid oxygen.

To determine the influencing factors on the reaction process, various energy levels must be tested, deviating from the standard procedure. The aim is to identify an energy level at which approximately 50% of the samples react. This allows for the detection of significant external changes in reactivity. In the context of this test series, the following energy levels were examined.

Energieniveau [J]	Eingestellte Fallhöhe [m]
22,3	0,250
30	0,336
40	0,448
56,3	0,631

Table 3 Overview of the investigated energy levels used in the experimental study. The energy level is derived from a 9.1 kg drop weight with varying drop heights.

For each energy level, ten samples from a single sample plate were tested. In addition to the reaction itself, the intensity of the reaction is also recorded.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the experiments, it was observed that, in addition to the number of reactions, differences in their intensity could also be identified. These variations influence, among other factors, the damage pattern of the specimen and the resulting chain reaction. The following figure illustrates the differences between various reactions and their respective intensities

Figure 6 Comparison of reaction intensity based on the light emission and the damage pattern of the specimen. For this purpose, three different specimens were examined under identical energy conditions of 56,3 Joule: a) AB68-L reaction of very low intensity b) AB100-L low intensity reaction c) AB90-L High intensity reaction

The recorded damage pattern not only quantifies the number of reactions but also provides insight into their intensity, allowing a more differentiated assessment of the various peel-ply fabrics. Figure 6 clearly demonstrates that different peel plies, and the resultant surface characteristics, significantly influence reaction intensity. At an impact energy of 56.3 J, specimens prepared with the finest peel ply exhibited the lowest reaction intensity.

This finding must now be correlated with the number of reactions observed at the respective energy levels and with the measured surface properties of the individual specimen series. **Table 4** summarises all detected reactions across the tested energy levels together with the corresponding surface parameters of each series.

Sample	FVC [%]	Ra [μm]	Rz [μm]	Spd [$1/\text{mm}^2$]	spk	vmp	Number of reactions for different Energy levels			
							22 [J]	30 [J]	40 [J]	56 [J]
AB68L-1	65,67	8,91	56,76	489,28	11,91	0,59	0	0	2	7
AB90L-2	66,97	12,8	78,57	448,52	22,71	1,1	1	2	9	10
AB100K-4	66,42	9,59	63,9	592,48	18,61	0,85	0	1	7	8
BLB-5	68,67	9	56,89	503,85	12,95	0,65	0	2	6	9
GP-8	66,69	0,28	1,95	-	-	-	0	0	0	0

Table 4 Representation of the identified reactions across various energy levels. In addition, the characteristic surface properties of each tested specimen plate are summarised. The table also includes the determined FVC values.

The experimental evaluation revealed that untreated base plates without peel ply produced the best results: no reaction was detected at any of the investigated energy levels. In contrast, the use of peel ply drastically altered the reaction behaviour, and all coated panels exhibited substantially more reactions. Among the peel plies tested, both the number and the intensity of reactions varied.

The 68 gsm peel ply yielded the most favourable results, with markedly lower reaction intensity. Surface roughness parameters as well as the reduced peak height and peak material volume recorded the lowest values. Although the number of surface asperities is lower than for the 100 gsm peel ply or the very fine Bleeder Lees fabric, which implies a higher induced energy per unit area, the considerably flatter asperities mean that less material must be compressed and destroyed before the striker contacts the remaining surface. Consequently, no significant difference between the BLB-5 and AB68-L specimens was observed, as their characteristic surface features differ only marginally.

The reaction behaviour of specimens with the AB100-K peel ply is particularly noteworthy. Despite a much higher asperity density compared with the other specimens, no significant difference in the number of reactions relative to BLB-5 was detected. Nevertheless, the AB100-K samples reacted far more intensely. This may be attributed to the taller asperities remaining on the surface, which permit a greater exothermic conversion of reactive material. This effect is also evident in the striker damage pattern depicted in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7 Surface alteration of the striker pin after an impact test at 56.3 joules for specimen material AB100-K. The specimen surface was imprinted onto the pin due to the impact. Areas of the striker that reacted with the liquid oxygen are clearly visible.

Although no substantial increase in the number of reactions was detected compared with the BLB experiments, the reaction intensity was markedly higher. As illustrated in **Figure 7**, this is reflected in the residual surface of the striker pin, onto which the specimen's surface profile is imprinted. Particular attention must be paid to the combustion pattern on the pin. While a uniformly distributed circular

reaction pattern is typically observed, the present results clearly indicate that the material reacted primarily along the protruding volumetric features of the specimen surface. Hence, the height of the residual asperities and thus the surface relief, constitutes a decisive factor, a conclusion that likewise applies to the AB90-L series.

The reaction behaviour of the AB90-L specimens is even more pronounced. Both the number and the intensity of reactions exceed those of all other series. Notably, AB90-L was the only plate to react at an impact energy of 22.3 J. This specimen exhibits the highest surface roughness and the lowest asperity density, resulting in the greatest induced energy per unit area. In addition, both asperity height and volume are maximised relative to the other specimens, so that a larger amount of reactive matrix material first comes into contact with the striker-pin during impact. This configuration accounts for the considerably stronger reactions observed. Sufficient material is present in the form of raised regions that are compressed and destroyed by the rapid impulse, thereby generating hot-spot zones that initiate and amplify exothermic reactions.

Furthermore, friction must be considered. *Gerzeski* [4] demonstrated that, despite a central impact and a fixed striker, relative movement of the pin is possible. The characteristically rough surfaces of the specimens augment such frictional effects, thereby promoting additional reaction events.

6 SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

The experiments conducted to determine the influence of surface characteristics generated by different peel-ply fabrics have clearly shown that increased surface roughness significantly affects compatibility performance. Compared with a smooth reference surface of the same material, a marked rise in both reaction frequency and reaction intensity was observed. The key findings are summarised in the diagram below.

Figure 8 Comparison of compatibility results for various test specimens differing in the applied peel-ply material and, consequently, in their characteristic surface roughness properties. The results were benchmarked against the untreated base plate without peel ply, which exhibited no reaction at any of the tested energy levels. a 5% deviation of the results was assumed, which is shown in the bar chart

The results demonstrate that not only the contrast between a smooth base plate and a peel-ply surface is relevant but the specific choice of peel ply itself also exerts a decisive influence. As asperity height and the associated volume of the residual surface protrusions increase, reaction intensity rises. Variations in surface-roughness parameters and in the characteristic asperity features, such as asperity density, height, and volume, clearly deteriorated compatibility, as evidenced by the early response of specimen AB90-L at 22.3 J.

These findings underline that the surface quality of test specimens is of critical importance. The surface configuration ultimately present in the finished component can significantly affect certification with respect to liquid-oxygen (LOX) compatibility. It is therefore essential to specify precisely whether a peel-ply surface is required and, if its use cannot be avoided, to what extent subsequent surface

finishing is feasible.

Future work should focus on a detailed characterisation of the residual surface features resulting from the peel ply. Further experimental work should include specimens with post-processed surfaces to assess how surface reworking affects compatibility results compared to both the original test series and the untreated base plate. In addition, a substantial increase in the number of specimens per experimental series is recommended to enhance statistical significance.

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